

NWO and ZonMw Open Access Monitor 2023

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Team

Hans de Jonge

Director, Open Science NL, Dutch Research Council (NWO)

Jeroen Sondervan

Programme Leader Open Scholarly Communication, Open Science NL, Dutch Research Council (NWO)

Bianca Kramer

Independent consultant, Sesame Open Science

Ellen Carbo

Project Leader FAIR Data and Open Access, ZonMw

NWO The Hague Postbus 93138 2509 AC Den Haag

Telephone: +31 (0)70 3440640 Email: nwo@nwo.nl

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Executive summary

In this report we analysed the openness of publications from research funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) and The Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMw) for the publication year 2023. This research has been conducted exclusively on openly accessible research information and metadata.

Overall, based on the available data, 94.6% of the articles analysed (6,254 out of 6,610) have been made available open access (OA) using one of the available open access routes. This is an increase compared to 2020 (85%), 2021 (90%) and 2022 (93%), it should be noted however that because of different data sources and methodology used in the previous studies comparisons need to be made with caution. This percentage is 94.8% for NWO-funded output and 91.9% for ZonMw. There is an overlap of 868 articles (13% of the total number of articles) that have received funding from both NWO and ZonMw.

At least 70% of the NWO and ZonMw funded publications from 2023 (4,633 out of 6,610) has been published open access immediately, with a CC-BY (or CC-BY-ND) licence, via either the Gold, Hybrid (under a transformative agreement) and for 8 papers the Green OA route. For this report we consider these publications as fully Plan S compliant, which is mandatory for NWO and ZonMw funds granted from 2021 onwards. It should be noted that the majority of the current publications analysed are most likely from grants awarded before 2021 and therefore fall under the previous open access policies of both NWO and ZonMw.

While 100 percent open access remains the goal for both funders, other aspects of open publishing are becoming ever more important, such as quality aspects of open access in general (i.e. proper use of licensing, adding funder acknowledgements if applicable, etc.). Internationally, concerns are growing about the dependency on an increasingly smaller group of commercial publishers for academic publishing, the rising costs associated with publishing, and the equity and accessibility of open access publishing for less well funded countries and regions in the world due to high publication costs.

NWO and ZonMw intend to continue their efforts in the coming years to contribute to a fairer, more equitable and diverse open publishing landscape.

1 Introduction

NWO and ZonMw are strongly committed to ensuring that the outputs resulting from their funding become openly available for reuse by anyone interested. NWO and ZonMw's first open access (OA) policies date back to the mid-2000's, followed by policies to ensure that research data produced in NWO and ZonMw funded research are managed properly and shared according to the FAIR principles. Over the years these policies have evolved and have been regularly updated.

In 2018 NWO and ZonMw joined cOAlition S, the international group of funding agencies that developed Plan S, a strategy to accelerate the transition to full and immediate open access to all (peer reviewed) publications that are the result of research funded by the participating funders. The requirements of Plan S apply to publications resulting from calls published by NWO and ZonMw from 1 January 2021 onwards. The mandate stipulates that all scholarly publications supported by NWO and ZonMw must be freely openly accessible upon publication, so without embargo, but and with retention of the copyrights, following one of the following routes:

- Publication in a fully open access journal registered in the [Directory of Open Access Journals \(DOAJ\)](#).
- Publication in a journal for which a transformative agreement exists.
- Deposition of a copy of the publication (the Version of Record or at least the Author Accepted Manuscript) in an open access repository registered in the [Directory of Open Access Repositories \(OpenDOAR\)](#).

In all cases, a [Creative Commons CC BY licence](#) must be applied to the publication. In exceptional cases, a [CC BY-ND](#) licence is allowed.

Open access monitoring at NWO and ZonMw

Since 2020, NWO and ZonMw have consistently monitored the progress on open access article publications. For the period 2020-2022 we collaborated with the Centre for Science and Technology Studies, CWTS at Leiden University. Publication data for these reports were retrieved from Web of Science (2020 and 2021) and Dimensions (2022), while the open access status was established using Unpaywall.¹

Since Web of Science and Dimension are commercial databases, NWO and ZonMw were unable to openly share the data underlying these analyses. That is why - in line with open science principles - for the OA monitor 2022 it was decided to move away from the use of these proprietary sources and from then on exclusively use openly available metadata to monitor open access progress.² In 2022 we used Crossref data in combination with Unpaywall. For the present monitor, covering the publication year 2023, we have enhanced this method by extending our corpus with publications data registered by NWO and ZonMw funded researchers in the grant systems of NWO (ISAAC) and ZonMw (MijnZonMw).

Importance of Open Research Information

The decision to move away from the use of proprietary databases and instead use open metadata sources is in line with NWO and ZonMw's strong commitment to open science. Not only do NWO/ZonMw have the ambition to ensure that the outputs of NWO/ZonMw funded research are made available open access, but wherever possible we also aim to apply the principles of openness to our own procedures, data and publications. In line

¹ Ludo Waltman, & Wout S. Lamers. (2022). Monitoring Open Access publishing of NWO-funded research (2015-2021) (Versie 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7105355>

² De Jonge, H., Sondervan, J., & Carbo, E. (2023). NWO and ZonMw Open Access Monitor 2022 (Versie 1). Dutch Research Council (INWO) and ZonMw. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10032907>

with this ambition, NWO and ZonMw signed the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information in April 2024.³ This new initiative aims to promote the openness of research information, more specifically, the openness of bibliographic metadata.

It is often argued that using open metadata instead of more established proprietary (but closed) bibliographic databases comes with drawbacks, especially in terms of coverage and completeness of the bibliometric data. Many of the larger commercial proprietary databases like Scopus, Web of Science and especially Dimensions have been investing in linking funding to publication output. It is estimated that Crossref is able to identify only around 50% of the total number of publications of a given funder.⁴ The reason is that a substantial number of publishers are slow or reluctant to deposit funding information to Crossref, and/or face difficulties in obtaining and processing funding information in publishing workflows.⁵

At the same time, the proprietary databases (especially Web of Science and Scopus) have their own issues with coverage, due to their selective nature. NWO and ZonMw strongly feel that the lack of coverage in open bibliographic resources should be balanced against the well-known problematic selectivity of the proprietary databases and their closed nature.⁶

By consciously and consistently using open metadata wherever possible, NWO and ZonMw hope to set an example that can be followed by other institutions and will in due course also lead to an increased availability and quality of openly available bibliographic data.

Therefore, all data underlying this report and the code used to collect and enrich the publication data are openly available (the DOI to the dataset can be found in the colophon).

³ 'NWO and ZonMw sign declaration to promote open research information' (April 2024). <https://www.nwo.nl/en/news/nwo-and-zonmw-sign-declaration-to-promote-open-research-information>

⁴ Bianca Kramer, Hans de Jonge; The availability and completeness of open funder metadata: Case study for publications funded by the Dutch Research Council. *Quantitative Science Studies* 2022; 3 (3): 583–599. doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00210

⁵ De Jonge, H. et al (2023). Open funding metadata through Crossref; a workshop to discuss challenges and improving workflows: <https://www.crossref.org/blog/open-funding-metadata-community-workshop-report/>

⁶ Basson, I (2022). The effect of data sources on the measurement of open access: A comparison of Dimensions and the Web of Science. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0265545>

2 Methodology

The sources from which data were aggregated and used for this report are discussed first (section 2.1), followed by the approach taken to identify publications funded by NWO or ZonMw (section 2.2), and how the OA status of these publications was determined (Section 2.3). We then discuss the scope of transformative agreements (section 2.4) and finally, we elaborate on how we estimate the Plan S compliance of publications (Section 2.5).

2.1 Data sources

The data and figures in this report rely on information gathered from the following open (meta)data sources and services:

- Crossref - the international non-for-profit membership organisation responsible for issuing DOI's for published academic works- to identify publications funded by NWO or ZonMw and to establish publication type and publication date;
- Unpaywall - to establish the OA status and embargo time;
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) - to check the Diamond OA status
- OpenAlex - to enrich the metadata with corresponding author information and disciplines.
- Plan S Journal Checker Tool - to check whether publications are covered under transformative agreements

All databases were queried using their respective APIs using Google Apps scripts (based on Javascript).

Data extraction from Crossref took place on the 21st of June, 2024. Data from Unpaywall, DOAJ and OpenAlex were collected between the 21st and 28th of June, 2024, and data from the Plan S Journal Checker Tool was collected on the 3rd of July, 2024.

In addition, all DOIs registered in 2023 and 2024 were collected and filtered for publications with a publication date in 2023.

2.2 Identifying publications funded by NWO or ZonMw

To identify publications from NWO and ZonMw we used two information sources.

Firstly, data from Crossref was retrieved. As of 2013 Crossref allows publishers to deposit funding information metadata when registering a DOI. To that end Crossref has developed the Funder Registry, an open registry of grant-giving organisation names and identifiers. This metadata can be accessed by using the Crossref REST API.

For this analysis publications were selected that could be identified by the funder ID for both NWO (10.13039/501100003246) and ZonMw (10.13039/501100001826) and the funder IDs nested under either of these in the hierarchy of funder IDs.

Query link: [NWO](#)

Query link: [ZonMW](#)

In addition, records were selected (and deduplicated) in which NWO and/or ZonMw were identified by their respective acronym: for this study we have only used these two abbreviations. We know that many other name variants exist, but for reasons of feasibility we have not considered these for collecting data (see for exploration section 3.9).

Query link: [NWO](#)
Query link: [ZonMw](#)

Secondly, data registered by grantees funded by NWO and ZonMw in their respective grant systems (resp. ISAAC and MijnZonMw) was collected. All DOIs registered in 2023 and 2024 were collected and filtered for publications with a publication date in 2023. It should be noted that this (meta)data is not openly available. However, both NWO and ZonMw are working on getting project data available as FAIR metadata.⁷

The year in which a publication was published was determined by the first publication date (print or online) supplied by the publisher to Crossref. Publications by researchers affiliated with NWO institutes were also included if these publications had NWO or ZonMw listed as funders or were reported in ISAAC or MijnZonMw.

Figure 1: Methodology of deduplication of (open) metadata sources and open indexes used for analyses.

Limitations and mitigation actions

We need to acknowledge a few limitations within this approach. Since we rely on funder acknowledgements and funding metadata from Crossref, we will very likely have missed publications, for which this information is not included in the metadata.

Some authors may have failed to acknowledge funding from NWO or ZonMw in their publications, or funding metadata could have been missing because publishers have not registered it with Crossref or registered only a funder name (with its many existing variants), not the funder id. To mitigate this limitation and to get a more complete corpus of outputs that can be traced back to funding from both organisations, we included (and deduplicated) the articles registered in NWO's ISAAC and ZonMw's MijnZonMw information systems.

Books, book chapters, publications in conference proceedings and other 'non-journal article' based outputs are not included in this analysis.

Despite the limitations, we believe the OA statistics in this report offer a reasonably complete overview of the extent to which publications funded by NWO or ZonMw have been made openly accessible and how that is done. Additionally, as NWO and ZonMw have been publishing this monitor in successive years, it does show the overall trend.

⁷ See for example: 'How to use the NWOOpen-API'. <https://www.nwo.nl/en/how-to-use-the-nwopen-api>

2.3 Determining the Open Access status of publications

The OA status of publications was determined by enriching the publication data with open access data from the Unpaywall database, as well as the OpenAlex database.

For each publication funded by NWO or ZonMw, the Unpaywall database was used to determine whether the publication is OA or not, and its OA type. The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) was used to distinguish between full OA journals that do or do not charge the author for publishing (by asking an Article Processing Charge – APC) and to distinguish full OA journals not in DOAJ.

Six types of open access are distinguished:

- **Diamond OA (in the dataset qualified as DOAJ - non-APC).** Publications in a full OA journal indexed in DOAJ that charges no fees (APCs) to both readers and authors.
- **Gold OA - DOAJ – APC.** Publications in a full OA journal indexed in DOAJ that charges fees (APCs).
- **Gold OA - non-DOAJ.** Publications in a full OA journal not indexed in DOAJ, for which the existence of fees is undetermined.
- **Hybrid OA.** OA publications in a subscription journal with a clearly identifiable open licence.
- **Bronze OA (in the dataset we distinguish ‘Bronze only’ and ‘Bronze and Acc/Green’, see below).** OA publications in a subscription journal without a clearly identifiable open licence.
- **Green OA (accepted manuscript/published version).** Publications that have the accepted manuscript or published version available in an open repository (e.g. in an institutional repository or on a preprint server).
- **Green OA (submitted version only).** Publications (mostly preprints) that only have a submitted version of the manuscript available in an open repository (e.g. in an institutional repository or on a preprint server).

Diamond, Gold, Hybrid, and Bronze OA are mutually exclusive. Green OA may overlap with the other types of OA. For instance, if a publication in an OA journal is also available in an OA repository, the publication is both Diamond or Gold OA and Green OA. In this report, we have chosen to classify a publication as Green OA only if it is not Diamond, Gold, or Hybrid. For Bronze OA, we have indicated whether a publication is also available as green OA (Bronze and Green acc/pub), or only as Bronze OA (Bronze only). In this way, each open access publication is classified as exactly one of the seven types of open access listed above.

The following caveats apply. In this overview we have chosen to include Bronze OA (Bronze only category) in the overview, given the very small number (n=66). Bronze OA publications lack an identifiable open licence. Their inclusion in the open access statistics presented in this report can be debated. In previous years manual examination on a random sample of Bronze OA publications was done. A majority of these publications in this sample seemed to be genuine open access publications. Based on this experience, and also because the subset is rather small, we decided to include bronze OA publications in the open access statistics in this report. However, due to the small number, these Bronze publications are not visible in some of the figures in this report.

We have also classified all manuscripts that only have a submitted version (based on Unpaywall data) as Green OA, but have included them separately in the overview. In most cases this concerns preprints. We’ve added this classification for two reasons: firstly, to make these versions more visible and secondly because these papers are openly available in one way or another.

Both the Bronze OA and Green OA (submitted only) categories are not Plan S compliant, but we have included them because these publications are available and therefore cannot be categorised as closed access. In section 3.7, ‘estimating Plan S compliance’, we will look into detail which papers can be identified as fully compliant with Plan S requirements.

Only publications made available through legal forms of open access publishing are considered in this report. Publications made available through Academic Social Network (ASN) platforms such as ResearchGate and

Academia.edu, or websites such as Sci-Hub or personal websites, are not considered to be openly accessible and are not included in the data.

A limitation must be recognised concerning the open access status of publications, since there might have been inaccuracies in the data from the Unpaywall database - either because of errors in detecting open access versions at publisher websites or repositories⁸, detection and classification of licences, or assignment of open access status based on these parameters.⁹ While Our Research, the organisation behind Unpaywall, is usually quick to remedy such issues when they detect them or they are pointed out to them, the presence of some inaccuracies will be inevitable given the dynamic nature of open access.

2.4 Establishing the scope of Transformative Agreements

Publications covered by transformative agreements (TAs) were traced by combining two open data sources. Data about journals covered by TA's were retrieved from the Journal Checker Tool (JCT) as developed by cOAlition S.¹⁰ TA's in the Netherlands are primarily negotiated by the national library consortium in the Netherlands (i.e. UKB), though a number of TAs have also been established between publishers and individual Dutch institutions.¹¹ Data on these TAs were also retrieved through the JCT. Agreements negotiated by UNL/UKB with publishers typically are only open to corresponding authors affiliated with a Dutch university. To establish whether a publication could have been covered by a TA, affiliation data had to be collected for all publications. This was done using the field 'corresponding institution' from OpenAlex. Finally, Unpaywall was used to determine the open access status of publications, as described before.

By combining these three sources we were able to establish whether open access publications in our dataset could have been covered by a transformative agreement and therefore likely paid from these contracts.

2.5 Establishing an overview of Plan S compliance

With the available data, we were able to assess the Plan S compliance of the included articles at a more detailed level. To calculate Plan S compliance we used the following criteria:

- publications published open access immediately, either in a Diamond or Gold open access journal, indexed in the DOAJ or;
- publications published open access immediately in hybrid journals covered by a Transformative Agreement, or;
- publications shared immediately through a trusted repository without an embargo.

In all cases, publications should have a CC BY or CC BY-ND licence.

We looked at the use of licences as well as the use of embargoes. When multiple Green OA versions were available for a publication (e.g. in multiple repositories), we looked at the use of licences and embargoes for all versions. With the cOAlition S Journal Checker public data feed we were able to connect Hybrid and Gold OA publications to current transformative agreements (i.e. Read & Publish deals in the Netherlands).

We did not specifically look at articles from grants that have to comply with Plan S conditions, as these conditions only became mandatory for calls published from 2021 onwards. In the current available funder

⁸ "Additional Wiley free access papers (bronze/hybrid?)" (Dec 2020) - [Unpaywall discussion group](#)

⁹ Jahn, et al. (2023, Nov. 7). Scholarly Communication Analytics: Analysing and reclassifying open access information in OpenAlex. https://subugoe.github.io/scholcomm_analytics/posts/oalex_oa_status/

¹⁰ www.journalcheckertool.org

¹¹ For a complete and up-to-date overview of Transformative Agreements in the Netherlands, see <https://www.openaccess.nl/en/in-the-netherlands/publisher-deals>

acknowledgements/information it is not (yet) possible to automatically check whether an article falls under this updated policy.

3 Findings

3.1 Open Access status of NWO and ZonMw funded journal articles from 2023

We were able to detect a total of 6,610 publications for NWO and ZonMw. Of these, a total of 356 (5.4%) publications were closed. All the other 6,254 publications were detected as having an open access version.

The table below shows a breakdown by the different OA types divided by funding organisation as well as totals.

OA types	All	%	NWO	%	ZonMw	%
Diamond OA (DOAJ - non-APC)	131	2.0%	130	2.4%	24	1.1%
Gold OA (DOAJ - APC)	1.836	27.8%	1332	25.0%	745	34.7%
Gold OA (non-DOAJ)	86	1.3%	60	1.1%	40	1.9%
Hybrid OA	3.442	52.1%	2875	53.9%	963	44.9%
Bronze OA only	66	1.0%	47	0.9%	31	1.4%
Green OA (accepted manuscript/publication)	562	8.5%	489	10.6%	136	6.5%
Green OA (submitted manuscript only)	131	1.0%	124	2.3%	29	1.4%
Closed	356	5.4%	277	5.2%	173	8.1%
Total	6610	100.0%	5334	100.0%	2144	100.0%
All OA		94.6%		94.8%		91.9%

Table 1: Percentual breakdown of OA types for NWO/ZonMw funded publications. For NWO and ZonMw there are overlapping publications because of acknowledgement for both funders.

The following graphs give a visual representation of NWO/ZonMw funded publications distributed according to OA-status.

OA status (n=6.610)

Figure 2: Total number of NWO/ZonMw publications (6.610) divided by OA type.

OA status NWO publications (n=5.334)

Figure 3: Total number of NWO publications (n=5.334) divided by OA type.

Figure 4: Total number of ZonMw publications (n=2144) divided by OA type.

The data and graphs show that publications from NWO are more dependent on the Hybrid OA and to a much lesser extent on the Green OA route, when compared with ZonMw output. A larger number of ZonMw publications have been published in a full open access journal with an APC.

This can partly be explained by the ZonMw approach, where since 2021 grantees could reserve a dedicated budget (EUR 5.000) for APCs before the start of their research, under the conditions that the money could only be claimed if the article was published via Gold OA, and met all Plan S requirements. This might have stimulated more researchers to choose Gold open access with an APC, instead of for example Green open access. For NWO open access costs for publication in full open access journals can be claimed within the annual material budget of EUR 15k per FTE. However, the material budget is used to pay for other eligible costs as well, which means that in practice the material budget is only partially used for open access publishing and therefore researchers could have prioritised the Green OA route. This may have influenced where and how grantees have published their papers.

Another explanation is that NWO and ZonMw research concerns different domains, as each domain might have other developments and preferences for routes. For instance, in the life and medical sciences (the fields where ZonMw is funding projects) there is potentially for a higher budget for publishing available and there are more fully open access journals to choose from.

3.2 Disciplines

Publications were classified by four main fields (i.e. Health Science, Life Sciences, Physical Sciences and Social Sciences (the latter including the Humanities) based on the classification used by OpenAlex. This classification is publication- and not journal-based.

NWO - Disciplines and OA types

Figure 5: Number and distribution of publications for the main 4 fields and different OA types of NWO funded research.

Overall, the percentage of open access versus closed publications is quite similar for the four main fields, ranging from 90% in the Social Sciences and Humanities to 94% in the Physical Sciences. Gold OA publishing remains considerably more common in the Health and Life Sciences (40%) than in the Physical Sciences (19%) and the Social Sciences (16%). Diamond OA publishing plays a very marginal role in all fields; however, most prominently within Physical Sciences (3%). Green OA publishing plays a more modest role in the Health and Life Sciences (6%) but a much more important role in the Physical Sciences (13%) reflecting the long tradition in some of the natural sciences of posting publications on preprint servers such as arXiv.

3.3 Publishers

We also looked at the top 20 publishers of the articles we analysed and how the OA types are distributed for those publishers. Crossref data was used to harmonise the names of the publishers.

Top 15 publishers and distribution of OA types (total # of articles = 5.913)

Figure 6: Top 15 publishers for NWO and ZonMw publications in 2023, with the distribution of OA types.

The dependency on the Hybrid model of open access can be clearly seen with the major traditional publishers. Gold OA (DOAJ and non-DOAJ) is still second for those publishers, except for the Springer Nature group. Within the top 20 there are four full Gold OA publishers, MDPI, Frontiers, PLOS and Copernicus, that publish their contents exclusively open access.

The number of publications published in MDPI and Frontiers have increased rapidly in the past years as we already observed in previous moniors , and which as a result are now occupying position #8 and #10 of the top 15 publishers. The highest number of closed publications (n=137) can be found with Elsevier, which is the largest publisher of NWO/ZonMw funded research. Diamond OA is more common within few publishers, primarily, Elsevier, Springer Nature and the Royal Society of Chemistry. A closer look at the Diamond OA journals is provided in 3.5.

3.4 Diamond Open Access

Diamond OA refers to Open Access journals and platforms that are free to both authors and readers. Authors are not faced with publication fees. Any costs are covered by other sources (often from institutional funding). Although non-APC OA publishing has been part of the scholarly communication landscape from as early as the 1990's, a renewed interest can be observed in the past two years. COALition S in collaboration with Science Europe has commissioned a landmark study to chart the vast archipelago of diamond OA journals in the world.¹² The importance of the diamond OA model was further underscored by Conclusions adopted by the European Council in may 2023 calling for a transparent, equitable, and open access to scholarly publications.¹³

¹² Bosman, Jeroen; Frantsvåg, Jan Erik; Kramer, Bianca; Langlais, Pierre-Carl; Proudman, V. (2021). *The OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 1: Findings*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558704>

¹³ Council of the European Union (2023) High-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing - Council conclusions (approved on 23 May 2023).

NWO has been a supporter of the diamond OA model for many years and has supported various initiatives in the area, such as Sci-Post, the Dutch national diamond open access platform www.openjournals.nl and Open Library of the Humanities.

The total number of articles published under the Diamond OA model remains modest. A total of 131 publications could be identified for this report. This may have been caused by our decision to restrict our collection to publications with a DOI. The total number of publications in Diamond OA is probably higher.

Table 2. Presents the top 20 Diamond OA journals (with regards to number of NWO and ZonMW-funded publications published in these journals). The diamond OA platform SciPost, supported for many years by NWO, ranks first with 19 articles. Next is the Royal Society of Chemistry which has several diamond OA journals in its portfolio. Diamond OA articles published at Elsevier and Springer / Nature are for the most part published in journals participating in the SCOAP3 consortium: the international collaboration in the high-energy physics community to convert traditional closed physics journals to open access.

<i>Publisher</i>	<i>Journal</i>	<i>#</i>
Stichting SciPost	SciPost Physics	15
	SciPost Physics Core	1
	SciPost Physics Proceedings	3
Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC)	Chemical Science	12
	Digital Discovery	1
	Energy Advances	2
	Sensors & Diagnostics	2
Springer Science and Business Media LLC	Journal of High Energy Physics *	9
	Living Reviews in Relativity	1
	The European Physical Journal C *	3
Elsevier BV	Physics Letters B *	9
	Water Science and Engineering	1
Universitätsbibliothek der Ruhr-Universität Bochum	IACR Transactions on Symmetric Cryptology	6
American Chemical Society (ACS)	ACS Central Science	6
The Open Journal	Journal of Open Source Software	4
MIT Press	Open Mind	4
Walter de Gruyter GmbH	Linguistics	2
	Zeitschrift für Sprachwissenschaft	1
Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision	TMG Journal for Media History	2

Table 2: Top 20 diamond OA journals and their publishers. Total amount of diamond OA articles is 131. Journals participating in SCOAP3 are indicated ().*

3.5 Licences

Licences provide individuals and organisations worldwide with a standardised method to grant copyright permissions for creative and academic works. Licences ensure proper attribution and allow others to copy, distribute, and utilise these works. A variety of licences are in use, Creative Commons licences being the most common.

Figure 7 presents a breakdown of publications and the licences applied for NWO/ZonMw funded papers in 2023.

Figure 7: Breakdown by licence for NWO and ZonMw funded publications.

Of the publications analysed, 79% have a CC-BY licence, the most liberal of the CC licences and fully Plan S compliant.

Distribution of identified open licenses (n=5970)

Figure 8: Distribution of identified open licences for NWO and ZonMw funded publications

For the remaining publications the majority has a CC-BY-NC (5.5%) or CC-BY-NC-ND (7.5%) licence. Less than 1% of the publications have a CC-BY-SA or CC-BY-NC-SA licence or an unspecified licence (classified by Unpaywall als 'other-oa' 'other') (6.7%).

The CC-BY-NC and CC-BY-NC-ND licences are not compliant with Plan S. Publishers with the highest percentage of publications with one of both licences (778 articles in total) include Elsevier (22.8%), Wiley (22.5%), Oxford University Press (13.3%), Taylor & Francis (6.9%), Royal Society of Chemistry (2.6%) and American Chemical Society (1.7%). Given that transformative agreements exist with all of these publishers, there is still room for improvement in negotiating compliant licence arrangements in (new) transformative agreements.

3.6 Embargo periods

For those articles that have been made available by means of the Green OA route (a deposit in a trusted repository) we established the delay in the number of months after which papers were made available. We used the date when the Crossref record for the publication was created as a proxy for the publication date, with the caveat that publication dates, as provided by publishers to Crossref, sometimes only contain the month and year of publication, and not the exact date.

For a subset of Green OA publications analysed, the Unpaywall data lacks information regarding when these publications became openly accessible. This primarily concerns publications made available through Pubmed Central. Consequently, for those publications we cannot ascertain whether they were made openly available immediately upon journal publication or at a later date.

Many publishers enforce embargo periods of up to 12 or 24 months and sometimes longer, when the Green OA route is applied. In the case of the Green OA route, Plan S requires either that the accepted version ('author accepted manuscript' – AAM) or the closed published version ('version of record' – VoR) of a publication is made immediately openly accessible in a repository. The Green OA route is supported by the Rights Retention policy as formulated by cOAlition S.

Green OA: embargo periods (in months)

Figure 9: Distribution of the different embargo periods for NWO and ZonMw publications.

We see considerable variation in embargo terms as is shown in figure 9. The majority of Green OA papers have a maximum embargo period of 6 months. This is partly an effect of the implementation of Article 25fa in the Dutch Copyright Law (Taverne-amendment), which allows researchers to make short scientific works publicly available through their institutional repository after 6 months.¹⁴ Even though these papers are publicly available, they are not compliant with NWO and ZonMw policies, which do not accept embargo periods. Therefore, this remains an area to be worked on in cooperation with the institutions in the coming years.

According to Unpaywall data, for 562 (81%) of the Green OA accepted/published papers funded by NWO or ZonMw and published in 2023 has been made available in a repository. 131 (19%) of the Green OA papers are 'submitted' versions only.

We must note that these statistics need to be interpreted with caution, since Unpaywall may not always be able to accurately distinguish between the submitted, accepted, and published version of a publication, Unpaywall takes a conservative approach, labelling a version as submitted if it cannot be established to be the published or accepted version. In the past we've found some cases where Unpaywall found, and prioritised, the published version in a repository, even if it's published in a full OA journal.

3.7 Transformative Agreements

Transformative agreements (TA's) have constituted an important part of the open access strategy in the Netherlands. Transformative agreement is an umbrella term for agreements negotiated between institutions (libraries, national and regional consortia) and publishers in which former subscription expenditures are repurposed to support open access publishing of the institutions' authors.¹⁵

In the Netherlands, the responsibility for these negotiations primarily lies with the national library consortium UKB, which has over the last decade negotiated a range of open access deals with publishers. In 2023, there

¹⁴ Sondervan, J. et al. (2021). Sharing published short academic works in institutional repositories after six months: The implementation of the article 25fa (Taverne Amendment) in the Dutch Copyright Act. (2021). *LIBER Quarterly: The Journal of the Association of European Research Libraries*, 31(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.53377/lq.10915>

¹⁵ As defined by the ESAC initiative: <https://esac-initiative.org/about/transformative-agreements/>

were 22 current contracts with all the major traditional publishers covering over 11.000 journals.¹⁶ NWO and ZonMw do not financially contribute to these deals (and have not since 2015). However, publications made open access under these transformative agreements are compliant with their Plan S aligned open access policy.

For this report we tried to analyse the effect of the transformative agreements on NWO and ZonMw funded research. How many of the NWO and ZonMw funded publications were covered by transformative agreements? Answering this question posed a number of challenges.

In principle, the Dutch library consortium UKB receives detailed information about which publications are covered by the contracts from the publishers. Unfortunately, however, this data is not (yet) made openly available. By combining data from the Journal Checker Tool developed by cOAlition S with data about corresponding authorship from OpenAlex, it is possible (see method section) to reason that a given open access publication could have been covered by transformative agreement and therefore are likely paid from these contracts.

Figure 10: Share of NWO and ZonMw funded publications covered by transformative agreements (TA) negotiated by the Dutch library consortium UKB and the breakdown to publishers.

Figure 10 shows the result of this analysis. It shows that more than 60% of publications in 2023 were (very likely) covered by the transformative agreements. The majority (54.5%) of these publications were papers in hybrid journals. Not surprisingly, Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley and ACS occupy the largest share in publications covered by TAs.

Noteworthy is the proportion of publications in hybrid journals that are outside the TAs, consisting of 200 publications (5%). These types of publications are not compliant with the requirements of Plan S. Also since 2015 NWO has not allowed its funds to be used for these publications.

¹⁶ Details of the current (and archived) contracts are published on www.openaccess.nl

3.8 Estimating Plan S compliance

At least 70.1% of the NWO and ZonMw publications analysed (4,633 out of 6,610) have been published open access immediately (defined as within one month of publication), either via the Gold, Hybrid, or Green OA route, with a compliant CC-BY (or CC-BY-ND) licence can be identified as Plan S compliant.

For publications made available via the Gold and Hybrid route, licences are the main factor determining Plan S compliance (in addition to inclusion in DOAJ for Gold OA journals and for coverage by TAs¹⁷ for Hybrid journals). For Green OA, both licensing and embargo times determine Plan S compliance. As shown in section 3.5, 71.4% of publications in our dataset have a compliant licence. Split out by type of OA, this percentage is 87.8% for diamond OA, 87.0% for Gold OA and 84.6% for hybrid OA, while for green OA, only 8.5% of publications have a compliant licence. Regarding embargoes, as shown in section 3.6, 11.7% of Green OA publications have an accepted/published version available with an embargo of less than 1 month. This indicates that for green OA, licensing and embargo times contribute to a similar extent towards (lack of) Plan S compliance. In only 1.4% (n=8), there is a Green OA version that has both a compliant licence and is made immediately OA.

Though our current approach is much more accurate in terms of completeness and data accuracy than the report of last year, it remains a challenge to properly determine Plan S compliance for all publications. We have now only looked at the totals, without tracing the individual publications back to awarded projects. Only then can it be determined with 100% certainty whether papers meet the requirements established from 2021 (the introduction of Plan S). For this, it is first of all important that funding information (funder name and project code) is included in the acknowledgments and can be tracked. This is something that we will bring further to the attention of researchers and publishers in the coming years. In the future both NWO and ZonMw will look into the use of Grant IDs, persistent identifiers for funder project codes, to facilitate matching grants to publications.

Nevertheless, based on the figures presented in this report, we can certainly conclude that the majority of articles are published through eligible routes. In the coming years, when monitoring papers and OA routes becomes more sophisticated and detailed, and more articles are published following the Plan S requirements, we expect to see an increase of this percentage.

3.9 Funding metadata

When registering a DOI for a publication publishers can include funding information as part of the metadata. This is important because it allows funders to track the publications which arise from their funding. Also in this report we have made use of funding metadata to identify publications based on NWO and/or ZonMw funding, which was further supplemented by publications registered by grantees in respectively ISAAC and MijnZonMw.

We have looked to what extent publications included in this report have funding metadata available in Crossref. Figure 11 shows that 85.6% of publications contains some kind of information on project funding but not necessarily identified NWO and/or ZonMw as the funder. 78.9% of publications contained at least some name variant of NWO and/or ZonMw. No less than 458 variants were found. To combat this confusion, Crossref introduced the Open Funder Registry with which funders can be identified with a persistent identifier. 72.7% of publications in our collection were rightly identified as linked to funding from NWO and/or ZonMw using the Crossref Funder ID.

¹⁷ Given the limitations of our approach detecting TA coverage (as described in section 3.7), we did not apply this as a criterion when assessing Plan S compliance of articles in hybrid journals. Based on our data, 1745 of 2913 hybrid articles with a compliant licence have a Dutch corresponding author and are covered by a Dutch TA. However, apart from possible inaccuracies in detecting TA coverage, articles could also have been covered by TAs for which co-authors were eligible, and papers could have been made available as Green OA with a compliant licence as well. In any case, we assume here this is a small number in the total of Hybrid OA.

Share of publications with funding metadata (n=6610)

Figure 11: Share of publications with some kind of funding information, publications rightly identifying NWO and/or ZonMw with its funder name and percentage of publications in which NWO and/or ZonMw is identified as funder with the Crossref funder ID.

As we have shown in earlier work, the extent to which publishers deposit funding information to Crossref varies substantially.¹⁸ Figure 12 shows a breakdown for the 20 largest publishers in our dataset. It can be clearly seen that there are a number of larger society presses (APS, RSC, ACS, APA and AIP) that deposit funding metadata for nearly all of their publications. However, the larger commercial publishers, like Elsevier, Wiley, Springer, Sage and Taylor and Francis, only reach percentages between 70 to 75%. Only half or even less than half of the publications published by MDPI, IOP and EDP identify NWO and ZonMw rightly as the funder of research by using the funder ID.

¹⁸ Bianca Kramer, Hans de Jonge; The availability and completeness of open funder metadata: Case study for publications funded by the Dutch Research Council. *Quantitative Science Studies* 2022; 3 (3): 583–599. doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00210

Funding metadata per publisher

Figure 12: Variation in presence of funding metadata for the 20 largest publishers in our dataset.

3.10 Estimating the costs of OA publishing

The costs associated with open access publishing research funded by NWO and ZonMw is largely unknown. Both NWO and ZonMw allow its grant money to be used to pay for publication fees (for full fold open access only). But since there is no detailed accounting on project level required by project leaders, it is unknown to NWO and ZonMw to which extent their budgets are being spent on open access publication. It is also largely unknown how much is being spend on the publications that are covered by the transformative agreements. Although most of the contracts are publicly available in the ESAC-registry, for most of them it is unknown how much is paid for APC's under these contracts. Given the growing concerns internationally about the rising costs associated with open access publishing, this is relevant information.

In an appendix to this report we have applied a novel, experimental method to *estimate* the costs associated with the publications data used in this report. The same method was recently used in a study commissioned by the French Open Science programme.¹⁹ This analysis makes use of openly available data collected under the OpenAPC project.²⁰ We have been able to collect average APC prizes for 84% of the publications in our dataset.

The many limitations associated with this approach and its experimental nature has led us to present the this analyses in an annex with the DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13885012>.

¹⁹ Antoine Blanchard, Diane Thierry, Maurits van der Graaf. Retrospective and prospective study of the evolution of APC costs and electronic subscriptions for French institutions. Comité pour la science ouverte. 2022. <https://dx.doi.org/10.52949/26>

²⁰ <https://openapc.net/>

4 Conclusions

The percentage of open access has increased to 94.6% for the publication year 2023 (from 85% in 2020, 90% in 2021 and 93% in 2022). However, caution is needed when comparing this report's outcome with percentages from the CWTS-analyses (2020 and 2021), as the method of collecting the data was different as described in the limitations section. Nonetheless, it is evident that we are making significant steps in advancing open access.

NWO and ZonMw remain committed to making available all publications resulting from their funding programs as open access. In the coming years, however, the commitment will go beyond just achieving 100% open access. Other quality aspects also require attention, such as the application of appropriate licensing, the reduction of embargo periods and the deposit of complete and high-quality metadata. Many of these actions are also related to Plan S compliance, which will gain importance in the coming years as there will be a growing number of publications resulting from projects that have received funding starting in 2021.

Alongside these actions to enhance the openness and reusability of NWO and ZonMw funded outputs, we note a growing concern, nationally and internationally, about the growing dependence on an increasingly smaller group of commercial publishers for academic publishing, the rising costs associated with publishing, and the equity and accessibility of open access publishing for less well funded countries and regions in the world due to high publication costs.

Furthermore, this report once again shows that there still is a lot of work to be done for publishers to step up their efforts to deposit funding information to Crossref. NWO and ZonMw will continue to work with publishers and with the Dutch library consortium UKB to ensure that quality and completeness of metadata, including funding metadata, becomes a more important part of the contractual arrangements between libraries and publishers.

In conclusion, NWO and ZonMw are committed to work on these topics with the different stakeholders involved to find better solutions that will enhance the open scholarly communication ecosystem.

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Contact address:

Laan van Nieuw Oost-Indië 300
2593 CE Den Haag
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